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Without cytomegalovirus infection, no Behçet disease

Research article

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

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Ilija Barukčić

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🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The relationship between Cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection and Adamantiades-Behçet's disease (BD) has been investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

Without CMV infection, no BD. Furthermore, CMV is a sufficient condition of BD. A significant cause-effect relationship between CMV and BD is given.

CONCLUSION:

Cytomegalovirus is the cause Adamantiades-Behçet's disease.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Adamantiades-Behçet's disease; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Adamantiades-Behçet's disease (BD) is a vasculitis characterized with a very wide array of clinical manifestations, including the classical trias recurrent oral aphthous ulcers, genital ulcers and iritis/uveitis. ¹ Benediktos Adamantiades (1875 – 1962) (see [Adamantiades, 1931](#)) - Behçet disease is named after Hulusi Behçet (1889–1948), a Turkish dermatologist, neither a winner of a Nobel Prize in medicine nor a Dean of a prominent medical school, who still recognized the main symptoms of this disease in 1924 (see [Behçet, 1937](#)). Finally, the name Mrobus Behçet was formally adopted at The International Congress of Dermatology in Geneva in September 1947. ² However, symptoms of this disease (see [Zouboulis, 2010](#)) have already been described earlier (see [Janin, 1772](#); [Planner and Remenovskiy, 1922](#)) and especially by Hippocrates of Kos (460–377 BCE) (Epidemion (book 3, case 7)) in the 5th century before current era (BCE). ³ · ⁴ The International Study Group (ISG) for Behçet disease published in 1990 some criteria for the diagnosis of BD. ⁵ The prevalence of BD varies from 3.8-15.9/100000 in Italy ⁶ up to 20-420/100000 in Turkey. ⁷ The aetiology of Behçet's disease is still unknown. The role of various environmental factors including viral agents like Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV)-1 and Cytomegalovirus (CMV) in the pathogenesis of BD is a matter of debate. Nonetheless, management of Behçet's disease is difficult ⁸ and there are no internationally accepted, standardized treatment strategies for BD. The drugs that have been used for the treatment of BD include colchicine, 5-ASA/sulfasalazine, corticosteroids (CS), immunomodulators, immunosuppressants, anti-tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and other. A growing level of evidence is supporting especially the use of anti-tumor necrosis factor- α therapy for BD. ⁹ In particular, etanercept (ETN) demonstrated efficacy against BD. ¹⁰ However, sometimes surgical therapy is unavoidable.

¹Skef W, Hamilton MJ, Arayssi T. Gastrointestinal Behçet's disease: a review. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2015 Apr 7;21(13):3801-12. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v21.i13.3801. PMID: 25852265; PMCID: PMC4385527.

²Tan SY, Poole PS. Hulusi Behçet (1889-1948): Passion for dermatology. *Singapore Med J.* 2016 Jul;57(7):408-9. doi: 10.11622/smedj.2016123. PMID: 27439529; PMCID: PMC4958720.

³Feigenbaum A. Description of Behçet's syndrome in the Hippocratic third book of endemic diseases. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 1956 Jun;40(6):355-7. doi: 10.1136/bjo.40.6.355. PMID: 13355940; PMCID: PMC509495.

⁴Verity DH, Wallace GR, Vaughan RW, Stanford MR. Behçet's disease: from Hippocrates to the third millennium. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 2003 Sep;87(9):1175-83. doi: 10.1136/bjo.87.9.1175. PMID: 12928293; PMCID: PMC1771837.

⁵Criteria for diagnosis of Behçet's disease. International Study Group for Behçet's Disease. *Lancet.* 1990 May 5;335(8697):1078-80. PMID: 1970380.

⁶Olivieri I, Leccese P, Padula A, Nigro A, Palazzi C, Gilio M, D'Angelo S. High prevalence of Behçet's disease in southern Italy. *Clin Exp Rheumatol.* 2013 May-Jun;31(3 Suppl 77):28-31. Epub 2013 Apr 2. PMID: 23557837.

⁷Azizlerli G, Köse AA, Sarica R, Gül A, Tutkun IT, Kulaç M, Tunç R, Urgancıoğlu M, Dişçi R. Prevalence of Behçet's disease in Istanbul, Turkey. *Int J Dermatol.* 2003 Oct;42(10):803-6. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-4362.2003.01893.x. PMID: 14521694.

⁸Hatemi G, Silman A, Bang D, Bodaghi B, Chamberlain AM, Gul A, Houman MH, Kötter I, Olivieri I, Salvarani C, Sfikakis PP, Siva A, Stanford MR, Stübiger N, Yurdakul S, Yazici H. Management of Behçet disease: a systematic literature review for the European League Against Rheumatism evidence-based recommendations for the management of Behçet disease. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2009 Oct;68(10):1528-34. doi: 10.1136/ard.2008.087957. Epub 2008 Apr 17. PMID: 18420940.

⁹Kobayashi K, Ueno F, Bito S, Iwao Y, Fukushima T, Hiwatashi N, Igarashi M, Iizuka BE, Matsuda T, Matsui T, Matsumoto T, Sugita A, Takeno M, Hibi T. Development of consensus statements for the diagnosis and management of intestinal Behçet's disease using a modified Delphi approach. *J Gastroenterol.* 2007 Sep;42(9):737-45. doi: 10.1007/s00535-007-2090-4. Epub 2007 Sep 25. PMID: 17876543.

¹⁰Melikoglu M, Fresko I, Mat C, Ozyazgan Y, Gogus F, Yurdakul S, Hamuryudan V, Yazici H. Short-term trial of etanercept in Behçet's disease: a double blind, placebo controlled study. *J Rheumatol.* 2005 Jan;32(1):98-105. PMID: 15630733.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Sun et al., 1996

Sun et al. ¹¹ investigated the presence of CMV DNA with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in formalin-fixed biopsy specimens of 4 BD patients and 22 control subjects. By PCR, CMV DNA was detected in 2 from 4 BD patients, but not in any of the normal control subjects.

Table 1. CMV DNA and Behçet's disease (Study of Sun et al., 1996).

		Behçet's disease		
		YES	NO	
CMV DNA	YES	2	0	2
	NO	2	22	24
		4	22	26

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = 0,67700320
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,01846154

p (IMP) = 1

p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/A) > 1,00000000

p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/(Not B)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 1,00000000

χ^2 (IMP— A_i) = 0,00

χ^2 (IMP— Not B_i) = 0,00

P Value (IMP) = 0,00000000

PROPORTIONS.

(a/A) × 100 = (2 / 2) × 100 = 100,00 %

(b/A) × 100 = (0 / 2) × 100 = 0,00 %

(c/ not A) × 100 = (2 / 24) × 100 = 8,33 %

(d/ not A) × 100 = (22 / 24) × 100 = 91,67 %

(a/B) × 100 = (2 / 4) × 100 = 50,00 %

(c/B) × 100 = (2 / 4) × 100 = 50,00 %

(b/ not B) × 100 = (0 / 22) × 100 = 0,00 %

(d/ not B) × 100 = (22 / 22) × 100 = 100,00 %

(A/N) × 100 = (2 / 26) × 100 = 7,69 %

(not A/N) × 100 = (24 / 26) × 100 = 92,31 %

(B/N) × 100 = (4 / 26) × 100 = 15,38 %

(not B/N) × 100 = (22 / 26) × 100 = 84,62 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 12,00000000

RR (sufficient condition) = Division By 0!

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division By 0!

Index of relationship (IOR) = 5,50000000

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,76923077

p(IOI)= 0,07692308

¹¹Sun A, Chang JG, Kao CL, Liu BY, Wang JT, Chu CT, Yuan JH, Chiang CP. Human cytomegalovirus as a potential etiologic agent in recurrent aphthous ulcers and Behçet's disease. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 1996 May;25(5):212-8. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0714.1996.tb01374.x. PMID: 8835817.

2.1.2. The study of Lee et al., 2005

The study of Lee is biased and has not been considered for reanalysed.¹² The prevalence of CMV in the control group is with 50/50 to high, which is not logically consistent. Sill, besides of a biased control group, 72/71 BD patients were CMV IgG positive. In other words, even the study of Lee et al. support the null-hypothesis: without CMV infection, no BD.

2.1.3. The study of Seoudi et al., 2015

The case-control study of Seoudi et al. (Centre for Clinical and Diagnostic Oral Sciences, Institute of Dentistry, Barts and The London School of Medicine and Dentistry, Queen Mary University of London, London, United Kingdom) investigated the serum samples of 54 BD cases and 28 healthy controls (HC). At the end, 27 of 54 BD cases and 19 of 28 HC were CMV IgG positive. The data of Seoudi et al. are not plausible. There is none information on the sensitivity and specificity of the laboratory kits used. The prevalence of CMV infection in the control group is not comprehensible. The study was not considered for our purposes.

¹²Lee EB, Kwon YJ, Shin KC, Song YW, Park CG, Hwang ES, Cha CY. Decreased serum level of antibody against human cytomegalovirus in patients with Behçet's disease. *Rheumatol Int.* 2005 Jan;25(1):33-6. doi: 10.1007/s00296-003-0394-0. Epub 2003 Nov 5. PMID: 14600786.

2.1.4. The study of Oner et al., 2018

Oner et al. (Department of Internal Medicine, Adiyaman University, Turkey) measured CMV immunoglobulin G (IgG) titers in 44 patients with BD and 69 healthy people (control group). CMV IgG values were positive in all patients. Oner et al. regarded values above the cut-off (cut-off for CMV IgG: 6.00 IU/mL) as CMV positive (see Oner et al., 2018). The mean age of the patients was 38 ± 10.37 years. It was not possible to identify the number of CMV positive controls in the publication of Oner et al. A prevalence of about 90 % assumed, the number of CMV positive control is set to 62 (see table 2).

Table 2. CMV IgG and Behçet's disease (Study of Oner et al. , 2018).

		Behçet's disease		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	44	62	106
	NO	0	7	7
		44	69	113

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,20520970$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = $0,02793602$
 p (SINE) = $1,00000000$
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/B) > 1,00000000$
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = $0,02793602$
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = $0,00$
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = $0,00$
 P Value (SINE) = $0,00000000$

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (44 / 106) \times 100 = 41,51 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (62 / 106) \times 100 = 58,49 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (0 / 7) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (7 / 7) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (44 / 44) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (0 / 44) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (62 / 69) \times 100 = 89,86 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (7 / 69) \times 100 = 10,14 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (106 / 113) \times 100 = 93,81 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (7 / 113) \times 100 = 6,19 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (44 / 113) \times 100 = 38,94 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (69 / 113) \times 100 = 61,06 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = Division By 0!
 RR (sufficient condition) = $1,11290323$

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division By 0!
 Index of relationship (IOR) = $0,06603774$

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU) = $0,32743363$
 p (IOI) = $0,54867257$

2.1.5. The study of Ghorbani et al., 2020

Ghorbani et al. (Department of Virology, School of Medicine, Iran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran) conducted a cross-sectional study including 103 Behcet's patients. CMV serological markers including IgM and IgG were tested and CMV DNA were examined. The mean age was 38.86 ± 8.76 in males and 39.35 ± 7.50 in females. CMV IgG was found in 98 of 103 cases. Ghorbani et al. (see [Ghorbani et al., 2020](#)) did not provide a control group, which need not be regarded as a limitation of this study. Under the assumption of a fair study design ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0$), a fictive control group can be calculated as follows. The age-specific seroprevalence of CMV within the population ($p_{\text{prevalence}}$) will be about 90%.¹³ Under conditions of a necessary condition relationship, the number of cases $E(\underline{B}_t)$ determines the number of controls $E(\underline{B}_t)$ as¹⁴

$$\text{Sample size (control group)} = E(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{E(a_t)}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t))} = \frac{98}{(1 - (0.9))} = 980 \quad (1)$$

We expect, that about $980 - 98 = 882$ of the controls will be CMG IgG positive (see table 3 with fictive control group).

¹³Huang KL, Lai YJ, Lee CY, Lin YJ, Tsai CC, Chu LC, You HL, Huang HN, Lan KC, Hsu TY. Seroprevalence and risk factors for cytomegalovirus infection among pregnant women in southern Taiwan, 2014-2015. *Taiwan J Obstet Gynecol.* 2022 Mar;61(2):323-328. doi: 10.1016/j.tjog.2022.02.022. PMID: 35361395.

¹⁴Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer - a causal relationship?. *Causation*, 18(11), 5–36. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7662247>

Table 3. CMV IgG and Behçet's disease (Study of Ghorbani et al., 2020).

		Behçet's disease		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	98	882	980
	NO	5	98	103
		103	980	1083

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,05145631$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,05659688
p (SINE) = 0,99538319
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,95145631
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,95145631

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,05659688
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,24
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,24
P Value (SINE) = 0,00460616

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (98 / 980) \times 100 = 10,00 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (882 / 980) \times 100 = 90,00 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (5 / 103) \times 100 = 4,85 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (98 / 103) \times 100 = 95,15 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (98 / 103) \times 100 = 95,15 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (5 / 103) \times 100 = 4,85 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (882 / 980) \times 100 = 90,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (98 / 980) \times 100 = 10,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (980 / 1083) \times 100 = 90,49 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (103 / 1083) \times 100 = 9,51 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (103 / 1083) \times 100 = 9,51 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (980 / 1083) \times 100 = 90,49 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 2,06000000
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,05717368

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 2,17777778
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,05145631

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,00000000
p(IOI)= 0,80978763

The data of Ghorbani et al. are characterized with limitations. The quality of the diagnosis is not clear. The CMV IgG cut-off value used by the authors is purely subjective. The sensitivity of the laboratory kit used to determine CMV IgG is not 100 %. Besides of all, the fictive control group has no influence on the final result. The relationship between CMV and BD will be stronger than suggested by the data of Ghorbani et al.

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*¹⁵ too.

2.2.1. Conditio sine qua non relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 4. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	<u>d</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher,

¹⁵Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (2)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution¹⁶. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

¹⁶Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (6)$$

2.2.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (7)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.5. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\bar{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\bar{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (9)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see Barukčić, 2019c, p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (10)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 10 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (11)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (12)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (13)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (14)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see Barukčić, 2019c, p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (15)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.2.6. Bonferroni correction

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realise. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple testing problem (see [Tukey, 1994](#)) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (16)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni multiple-comparison correction (see [Bonferroni, 1936](#); [Dunn, 1961](#)) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Example

An investigation is testing $m = 20$ hypotheses with a desired $\alpha = 0.05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be of appropriate use. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance α_i given as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{0,05}{20} = 0,0025 \quad (17)$$

where m is the total number hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By requiring a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several trials to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these attempts is the so called Rom's Method published 1990 by Rom (see [Rom, 1990](#)) himself.

2.2.7. Bias

Many times, potential publication bias among the studies is assessed by Begg's funnel plot ¹⁷ , ¹⁸ , ¹⁹ , ²⁰ with something like a treatment effect (horizontal axis) and some measure of weight (inverse variance, standard error, sample size et cetera) on the vertical axis . It is not always an easy task to bring various studies together which differ in different aspects in order to re-analyse the same or for doing a meta-analysis. Due to several reasons, variability in the data of the studies and other difference might

¹⁷Light RJ, Pillemer DB. *Summing up. The science of reviewing research.* Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1984.

¹⁸Egger M, Davey Smith G, Schneider M, Minder C. Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple, graphical test. *BMJ.* 1997 Sep 13;315(7109):629-34. doi: 10.1136/bmj.315.7109.629. PMID: 9310563; PMCID: PMC2127453.

¹⁹Begg CB, Mazumdar M. Operating characteristics of a rank correlation test for publication bias. *Biometrics.* 1994 Dec;50(4):1088-101. PMID: 7786990.

²⁰Lau J, Ioannidis JP, Terrin N, Schmid CH, Olkin I. The case of the misleading funnel plot. *BMJ.* 2006 Sep 16;333(7568):597-600. doi: 10.1136/bmj.333.7568.597. PMID: 16974018; PMCID: PMC1570006.

be found. These days the heterogeneity among the studies is assessed through a so called I^2 statistics²¹,²²,²³ to. Under usual circumstances, an I^2 value of 25%, 50% and 75% are regarded as low, moderate and high heterogeneity²⁴. In this investigation, we preferred to control the study (design) bias and the heterogeneity among the studies by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) and by IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019b).

2.2.8. Sample size

In scientific practice, the truth is not known from the very beginning, but often need to be discovered in arduous detail work. However, under usual circumstances, it is impossible to study an entire population. So this is more or less one of the reasons why studies are conducted on samples drawn from a population and investigated. In the course of further investigations, conclusions are drawn from samples²⁵ and generalised to the population. In this regard, a sample as such should be a perfect representative of the population studied, independent of any sample size. It comes therefore as no surprise that a larger sample size might be a better representative of a certain population and will hence provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, an increase in sample size is not worth the effort. In other words, proper methods of study design and sampling should be used while the prevalence of an event within a population can be considered accurately. In this process of insight, there are some mistakes which can occur. Especially, a null hypothesis which is true can incorrectly be rejected and the either way. A null hypothesis which is false can incorrectly be accepted. However, one key aspect when designing an experiment or a clinical study et cetera, is the calculation of an appropriate sample size. A sample size is the number of experimental units or measurements (i.e. the number of patients in a medical study) et cetera needed to be included into a study in order to answer a certain research question. Therefore, an accurate pre-study calculation of the sample size²⁶ is of great importance. Nonetheless, it is worthy of attention that methods to calculate the sample size which are explained in statistical textbooks in more detail are prone to errors and changes in the selected parameters can lead to significant differences in the sample size. In fact, our experience so far has taught us, that a sample size which is too small, is tending to make it impossible to detect any difference or effect. In complete contrast to a small sample size, a sample that is larger than necessary might be a better representative of a certain population and may provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, a sample that is too large may amplify differences and induce a waste of time and money. Thus far, are large studies really more reliable than smaller studies, are smaller studies completely worthless? Despite of

²¹Cochran WG. The combination of estimates from different experiments. *Biometrics* 1954; 10(1): 101-29.

²²Higgins JP, Thompson SG. Quantifying heterogeneity in a meta-analysis. *Stat Med*. 2002 Jun 15;21(11):1539-58. doi: 10.1002/sim.1186. PMID: 12111919.

²³Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

²⁴Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

²⁵Faber J, Fonseca LM. How sample size influences research outcomes. *Dental Press J Orthod*. 2014 Jul-Aug;19(4):27-9. doi: 10.1590/2176-9451.19.4.027-029.ebo. PMID: 25279518; PMCID: PMC4296634.

²⁶Hickey GL, Grant SW, Dunning J, Siepe M. Statistical primer: sample size and power calculations-why, when and how? *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg*. 2018 Jul 1;54(1):4-9. doi: 10.1093/ejcts/ezy169. PMID: 29757369; PMCID: PMC6005113.

all the incontestable benefits of studies with a large sample size, a variety of biases²⁷ of studies with large sample size like measurement error, aggregation error, sampling error, multiple comparisons errors et cetera have been identified. In point of fact, studies with a large sample size can magnify the bias associated with error resulting from study design or sampling and so on. The issue of sample size is more or less not as simple as is often desired or assumed. Alongside undeniable scientific progress supported by studies, there are shortcomings and obvious delays and a particular caution and constant watchfulness and reserve is necessary, independently of the sample size of a study. In principle, even studies with a small sample size can play an important role in helping us recognise a certain relationship between events. Thus far and for illustration purposes only, let us suppose that a small study is investigating the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human being alive. Only three subjects were investigated, the following data were obtained and published.

Table 5. Gaseous oxygen and human being alive

		Human being alive B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen A_t	TRUE	1	1	2
	FALSE	0	1	1
		1	2	3

Are the results of such a study completely irrelevant? Under normal circumstances, our confidence into a relationship identified is running high, parallel with an increasing sample size. In contrast to a very large sample size, even a study with a very small sample size ($N = 3$) or even one single study is capable of identifying a fundamental relationship i.e. between gaseous oxygen and human life, it depends as always on the concrete circumstances. Human experience teaches us however that the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life as established before is true even if the sample size of the study presented is very small. As is well known, it is rarely possible to study the entire population. Nonetheless, further studies despite a larger sample size must be able to confirm the relationship established before in principle, independently of any potential difficulties.

Type I Error (Alpha)

The type I error is also called alpha or the significance level or the P Value and represents the chance or the probability to decide that two groups investigated differ while in reality these two groups do not differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-positive conclusion. Under usual circumstances, alpha is fixed at 0.05, which indicates that a researcher desires a less than 5% chance of drawing a false-positive conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because positive. The P Value is the probability obtained of incorrectly accepting the alternate hypothesis. The P Value is compared to the the significance level α to determine whether the result is statistically significant. The lower the P Value, the lower the probability of obtaining that result if a null hypothesis were true.

²⁷Kaplan RM, Chambers DA, Glasgow RE. Big data and large sample size: a cautionary note on the potential for bias. *Clin Transl Sci.* 2014 Aug;7(4):342-6. doi: 10.1111/cts.12178. Epub 2014 Jul 15. PMID: 25043853; PMCID: PMC5439816.

Type I and type II errors

Type I error: A true null hypothesis is rejected. **Type II error:** A false null hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 1. Today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error.

Power (1-Beta)

The type II error is also called beta and represents the chance or the probability to decide that the two groups investigated do not differ (no difference), while in reality these two groups do differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-negative conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because negative. Usually, beta is set at a level of 0.20. In other words, a researcher desires a less than 20% chance of a false-negative conclusion. Nonetheless, for the calculation of the sample size, it is necessary to consider the following relationship.

$$\beta + \text{power} = 1 \quad (18)$$

Consequently, power is the complement of beta, i.e. $\text{power} = 1 - \beta$. Thus far, if beta is 0.20, then the power is 0.80 or 80%. The power indicates the probability or the chance to avoid a false-negative conclusion or, in other words, the probability to detect a specified effect, assumed that the same really exists.

What is very interesting is that today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error excludes the possibility of a joint distribution between Type I error and Type II error, as demonstrated by figure ²⁸ 1. In other words, theoretically, it appears not to be possible that a null-

²⁸Serdar CC, Cihan M, Yücel D, Serdar MA. Sample size, power and effect size revisited: simplified and practical approaches in

hypothesis is false in reality (α) and that a statistical test tell us at the same time that a null-hypothesis is false (β) too. In the long run, this shortcoming may turn out to be unsustainable.

Table 6. Today's relationship between α and β

		R E S E A R C H		
		H ₀ is TRUE	H _A is TRUE	
R E A L I T Y	H ₀ is TRUE	$1 - \alpha$	α	1
	H _A is TRUE	β	$1 - \beta$	1
		$1 - \alpha + \beta$	$1 + \alpha - \beta$	2

pre-clinical, clinical and laboratory studies. *Biochem Med (Zagreb)*. 2021 Feb 15;31(1):010502. doi: 10.11613/BM.2021.010502. Epub 2020 Dec 15. PMID: 33380887; PMCID: PMC7745163.

3. Results

3.1. *If CMV infection of a specimen, then BD.*

Sun et al. ²⁹ investigated the presence of CMV DNA with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in formalin-fixed biopsy specimens of BD patients (see table 1) and identified a significant sufficient condition relationship between CMV infection and BD (p (IMP) = 1,0 ; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,018461538 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_t) = 0 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_t) = 0 ; P Value (IMP) = 0).

3.2. *Without CMV infection, no BD.*

Oner et al. (see Oner et al., 2018) investigated the relationship between CMV IgG and BD and found a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship (see table 2). In other words, without CMV infection, no BD (p (SINE) = 1 ; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,027936015 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0 ; P Value (SINE) = 0).

Ghorbani et al. did not provide a control group. However, the data of Ghorbani et al. are still of use. Even Ghorbani et al. (see table 2) provided evidence that a CMV infection is a necessary condition of BD (p (SINE) = 0,995383195 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,242718447 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,242718447 ; P Value (SINE) = 0,004606164).

3.3. *CMV infection is the cause of BD.*

Sun et al. (see table 1) provided additional evidence of a potentially significant causal relationship (causal relationship $k = +0,6770032$; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,018461538). In addition, Oner et al. (see Oner et al., 2018) determined a positive causal relationship between CMV and BD (causal relationship $k = 0,205209698$; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,027936015) even if $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,54867257$ was equally highly unfair. In other words, there is some very slight evidence that there is a causal relationship between CMV and BD.

²⁹Sun A, Chang JG, Kao CL, Liu BY, Wang JT, Chu CT, Yuan JH, Chiang CP. Human cytomegalovirus as a potential aetiologic agent in recurrent aphthous ulcers and Behçet's disease. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 1996 May;25(5):212-8. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0714.1996.tb01374.x. PMID: 8835817.

3.4. CMV and treatment

Based on the assumption that the discovered relationship between CMV and BD can be confirmed by other study groups, the following proposal of a treatment of a CMV infection should be initiated, supervised and monitored by a medical specialist experienced with the drugs suggested. The scientific justification for the proposed medications follows as next.

Table 7. CMV infection: Additional therapy

Data:	Name	First name	Birthday	Place of residence	Phone	E-Mail	Approved by
Drug	Immunoglobulin	Leflunomide	Etoricoxib	Etanercept	Valaciclovir	Atorvastatin	Cimetidin
Dosage	1 g per kg i.v. qd	10 mg qd or 20 mg p.o. qd	30 mg or 90 mg p.o. qd	10 mg or 25 mg or 50 mg s.c.	2 g p. o. qid	80 mg qd	800 mg qd
Month:							
Day:							
1	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
2		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
3	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
4		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
5	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
6		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
7		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
8		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
9		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
10		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
11		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
12		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
13		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
14		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
15		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
16		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
17		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
18		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
19		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
20		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
21		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
22		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
23		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
24		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
25		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
26		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
27		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
28		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
29		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
30		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
31		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0

Abbreviations. q.i.d.: quater in die (four times a day). t.i.d.: ter in die (three times a day). b.i.d.: bis in die (twice a day). q.d.: quaque die (once a day).

3.4.1. CMV and Immunoglobulin

Intravenous immunoglobulin (IV IgG) therapy (1 g per kilogram per day for 2-3 days) against COVID-19 infection has been demonstrated to be clinically effective.^{30, 31, 32} There is no reasonable argument to assume why this should be different for CMV. The use of CMV immunoglobulin³³ (CMVIG) is also a possible option. Dosage would also depend on the severity of the disease, while measures of clinical, laboratory (CMV antibodies) and other monitoring are of high importance in each case. Feinstein et al.³⁴ investigated whether intravenous immunoglobulin given at a dose of 500 mg/kg/wk might decrease the risk of a CMV infection (see table 8).

Table 8. The relationship between IV IgG and CMV infection (Study of Feinstein et al., 1999).

		CMV infection		
		YES	NO	
IV IgG	YES	3	117	120
	NO	10	111	121
		13	228	241

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,12758601$
 p (EXCL) = 0,98755187
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,04318195
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,01237098

However, I consider it quite remarkable that Feinstein et al. were able to provide statistically significant evidence that intravenous immunoglobulin given at a dose of 500 mg/kg/wk does decrease the risk of a CMV infection (p (EXCL) = 0,98755187; P Value (EXCL) = 0,01237098).

3.4.2. CMV and Leflunomide

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) infections are associated with increased morbidity and mortality and poses a major challenge for patient and physicians. Leflunomide or (N-(4'-trifluoromethylphenyl)-5-methylisoxazole-4-carboxamide) is an inhibitor of protein kinase activity and pyrimidine synthesis

³⁰Schultz NH, Sørvoll IH, Michelsen AE, Munthe LA, Lund-Johansen F, Ahlen MT, Wiedmann M, Aamodt AH, Skattør TH, Tjønnfjord GE, Holme PA. Thrombosis and Thrombocytopenia after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 Vaccination. *N Engl J Med.* 2021 Jun 3;384(22):2124-2130. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2104882. Epub 2021 Apr 9. PMID: 33835768; PMCID: PMC8112568.

³¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2021, April 18). Comment on Thrombosis and Thrombocytopenia after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 Vaccination (Version 2). Version 2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4707741>

³²Xiang HR, Cheng X, Li Y, Luo WW, Zhang QZ, Peng WX. Efficacy of IVIG (intravenous immunoglobulin) for corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19): A meta-analysis. *Int Immunopharmacol.* 2021 Jul;96:107732. doi: 10.1016/j.intimp.2021.107732. Epub 2021 Apr 30. PMID: 34162133; PMCID: PMC8084608.

³³Santhanakrishnan K, Yonan N, Iyer K, Callan P, Al-Aloul M, Venkateswaran R. Management of ganciclovir resistance cytomegalovirus infection with CMV hyperimmune globulin and leflunomide in seven cardiothoracic transplant recipients and literature review. *Transpl Infect Dis.* 2022 Feb;24(1):e13733. doi: 10.1111/tid.13733. Epub 2021 Oct 5. PMID: 34534396.

³⁴Feinstein LC, Seidel K, Jocum J, Bowden RA, Anasetti C, Deeg HJ, Flowers ME, Kansu E, Martin PJ, Nash RA, Storek J, Etzioni R, Applebaum FR, Hansen JA, Storb R, Sullivan KM. Reduced dose intravenous immunoglobulin does not decrease transplant-related complications in adults given related donor marrow allografts. *Biol Blood Marrow Transplant.* 1999;5(6):369-78. doi: 10.1016/s1083-8791(99)70013-3. PMID: 10595814.

and is easily given orally. Leflunomide works by inhibiting virion assembly.^{35 36} It has been shown that Leflunomide is effective^{37 38} against cases of CMV infection too.^{39 , 40 , 41}

3.4.3. CMV and Etanercept

It is known that tumour necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) is able to mediate host-resistance against micro-organisms and inhibits at the end CMV replication. Especially, serum TNF- α is found to be elevated during acute CMV-infections.⁴² Unfortunately, tumour necrosis factor alpha is a very powerful cytokine with a very ‘dark side’ too. It is now clear that TNF- α is involved causally in various pathological processes including malignant disease.⁴³ Anti-tumour necrosis factor alpha antibody therapy with TNF- α blocking agents like etanercept^{44 , 45}, infliximab and adalimumab provide a strategic option to block the pivotal role of TNF- α in the pathological pathway of (lung) cancer. In the case that a relationship between CMV and LC can be established, serum TNF- α could be of use to monitor LC therapy.

3.4.4. CMV and Valacyclovir

Currently available options for CMV treatment and prophylaxis present various challenges related to cost and side effects. Stephanie Lam (Department of Haematology, Fiona Stanley Hospital, Perth, Australia) et al. investigated whether prophylaxis with high dose valaciclovir is effective at reducing CMV infection. Patients were treated with 2g valaciclovir orally four times daily. “Forty-nine patients

³⁵Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Blinder L, Shen J, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Inhibition of cytomegalovirus in vitro and in vivo by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Intervirology*. 1999;42(5-6):412-8. doi: 10.1159/000053979. PMID: 10702725.

³⁶Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Novel mechanism of inhibition of cytomegalovirus by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Transplantation*. 1999 Sep 27;68(6):814-25. doi: 10.1097/00007890-199909270-00014. PMID: 10515382.

³⁷John GT, Manivannan J, Chandy S, Peter S, Jacob CK. Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation*. 2004 May 15;77(9):1460-1. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000122185.64004.89. PMID: 15167608.

³⁸Avery RK, Bolwell BJ, Yen-Lieberman B, Lurain N, Waldman WJ, Longworth DL, Taeye AJ, Mossad SB, Kohn D, Long JR, Curtis J, Kalaycio M, Pohlman B, Williams JW. Use of leflunomide in an allogeneic bone marrow transplant recipient with refractory cytomegalovirus infection. *Bone Marrow Transplant*. 2004 Dec;34(12):1071-5. doi: 10.1038/sj.bmt.1704694. PMID: 15489872.

³⁹Sudarsanam TD, Sahni RD, John GT. Leflunomide: a possible alternative for ganciclovir sensitive and resistant cytomegalovirus infections. *Postgrad Med J*. 2006 May;82(967):313-4. doi: 10.1136/pgmj.2005.038521. PMID: 16679469; PMCID: PMC2563786.

⁴⁰John GT, Manivannan J, Chandy S, Peter S, Jacob CK. Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation*. 2004 May 15;77(9):1460-1. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000122185.64004.89. PMID: 15167608.

⁴¹Suissa S, Bernatsky S, Hudson M. Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2006 Aug 15;55(4):531-6. doi: 10.1002/art.22094. PMID: 16874796.

⁴²Haerter G, Manfras BJ, de Jong-Hesse Y, Wilts H, Mertens T, Kern P, Schmitt M. Cytomegalovirus retinitis in a patient treated with anti-tumor necrosis factor alpha antibody therapy for rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2004 Nov 1;39(9):e88-94. doi: 10.1086/425123. Epub 2004 Oct 11. PMID: 15494900.

⁴³Balkwill F. TNF-alpha in promotion and progression of cancer. *Cancer Metastasis Rev*. 2006 Sep;25(3):409-16. doi: 10.1007/s10555-006-9005-3. PMID: 16951987.

⁴⁴Hung YM, Lin L, Chen CM, Chiou JY, Wang YH, Wang PY, Wei JC. The effect of anti-rheumatic medications for coronary artery diseases risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis might be changed over time: A nationwide population-based cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2017 Jun 28;12(6):e0179081. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0179081. PMID: 28658301; PMCID: PMC5489160.

⁴⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2020). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of human atherosclerosis. *International Journal Of Current Science Research*. Volume: 6; Issue: 1; January-2020; pp 1912-1938. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3902775>

in the prophylaxis group and 59 in the control group were included ... There was no CMV disease in the prophylaxis group and three cases in the control group. ⁴⁶ In other words, **without treatment with 2g valaciclovir orally four times daily no absence of a CMV infection**. Hawks et al. found that valacyclovir 1 g three times daily with affordable cost and a favourable toxicity profile is an option for CMV prophylaxis ⁴⁷ and therapy too. ⁴⁸

3.4.5. CMV and Cimetidine

Cimetidine is an H₂ receptor antagonist ⁴⁹ with the indication of gastroesophageal reflux disease, peptic ulcer disease, urticaria, and other. Cimetidine affects even the pharmacokinetics of other drugs. The effects of cimetidine, probenecid and of other drugs on the pharmacokinetics of valacyclovir have been investigated. ⁵⁰ Cimetidine (800 mg bid) inhibit excretion of valacyclovir and, thus, potentiate antiviral concentrations of serum while not affecting the tolerability of valacyclovir. ⁵¹, ⁵²

3.4.6. CMV and Etoricoxib

Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) is an enzyme involved in pain and inflammation. Selective inhibitors of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) might downregulate COX-2 and decrease inflammation and pain. Etoricoxib ⁵³ as member of the class of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) is a highly selective inhibitor of cyclooxygenase-2. The long plasma half-life of etoricoxib allows the use of etoricoxib ⁵⁴

⁴⁶Lam S, Boan P, Polistena P, Cannell P, Cooney J, Wright M, Purtill D. High dose valaciclovir to prevent cytomegalovirus infection in allogeneic haematopoietic stem cell transplant recipients. *Transpl Infect Dis*. 2021 Aug;23(4):e13633. doi: 10.1111/tid.13633. Epub 2021 Jun 1. PMID: 33978289.

⁴⁷Hawks KG, Fegley A, Sabo RT, Roberts CH, Toor AA. High dose valacyclovir for cytomegalovirus prophylaxis following allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation. *J Oncol Pharm Pract*. 2023 Jan;29(1):130-137. doi: 10.1177/10781552211060479. Epub 2021 Dec 2. PMID: 34854771.

⁴⁸Shahar-Nissan K, Pardo J, Peled O, Krause I, Bilavsky E, Wiznitzer A, Hadar E, Amir J. Valaciclovir to prevent vertical transmission of cytomegalovirus after maternal primary infection during pregnancy: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2020 Sep 12;396(10253):779-785. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31868-7. Erratum in: *Lancet*. 2020 Oct 10;396(10257):1070. PMID: 32919517.

⁴⁹Pino MA, Azer SA. Cimetidine. 2022 May 1. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-. PMID: 31334975.

⁵⁰De Bony F, Tod M, Bidault R, On NT, Posner J, Rolan P. Multiple interactions of cimetidine and probenecid with valaciclovir and its metabolite acyclovir. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2002 Feb;46(2):458-63. doi: 10.1128/AAC.46.2.458-463.2002. PMID: 11796358; PMCID: PMC127018.

⁵¹Lerner AM, Beqaj SH, Deeter RG, Fitzgerald JT. Valacyclovir treatment in Epstein-Barr virus subset chronic fatigue syndrome: thirty-six months follow-up. *In Vivo*. 2007 Sep-Oct;21(5):707-13. PMID: 18019402.

⁵²Purifoy DJ, Beauchamp LM, de Miranda P, Ertl P, Lacey S, Roberts G, Rahim SG, Darby G, Krenitsky TA, Powell KL. Review of research leading to new anti-herpesvirus agents in clinical development: valaciclovir hydrochloride (256U, the L-valyl ester of acyclovir) and 882C, a specific agent for varicella zoster virus. *J Med Virol*. 1993;Suppl 1:139-45. doi: 10.1002/jmv.1890410527. PMID: 8245881.

⁵³Ong SWX, Tan WYT, Chan YH, Fong SW, Renia L, Ng LF, Leo YS, Lye DC, Young BE. Safety and potential efficacy of cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors in coronavirus disease 2019. *Clin Transl Immunology*. 2020 Jul 26;9(7):e1159. doi: 10.1002/cti2.1159. PMID: 32728438; PMCID: PMC7382954.

⁵⁴Wu LC, Leong PY, Yeo KJ, Li TY, Wang YH, Chiou JY, Wei JC. Celecoxib and sulfasalazine had negative association with coronary artery diseases in patients with ankylosing spondylitis: A nation-wide, population-based case-control study. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2016 Sep;95(36):e4792. doi: 10.1097/MD.0000000000004792. PMID: 27603385; PMCID: PMC5023908.

· ⁵⁵ for once-daily dosing. ⁵⁶ The study group around Hung et al. provided some **very slight and indirect evidence** that etoricoxib is of help against CMV infection too. ⁵⁷ Further investigations are needed to decipher the relationship between etoricoxib and CMV infection in its entirety.

⁵⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2020). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of human atherosclerosis. *International Journal Of Current Science Research*. Volume: 6; Issue: 1; January-2020; pp 1912-1938. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3902775>

⁵⁶Matsumoto AK, Cavanaugh PF Jr. Etoricoxib. *Drugs Today (Barc)*. 2004 May;40(5):395-414. PMID: 15319795.

⁵⁷Hung YM, Lin L, Chen CM, Chiou JY, Wang YH, Wang PY, Wei JC. The effect of anti-rheumatic medications for coronary artery diseases risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis might be changed over time: A nationwide population-based cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2017 Jun 28;12(6):e0179081. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0179081. PMID: 28658301; PMCID: PMC5489160.

3.4.7. CMV and statins

Statins are commonly used drugs to lower cholesterol levels through inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme (HMG-CoA) reductase. Benjamin D Horne et al. evaluated in a prospective study the effect of statins on CMV and found that statins have beneficial antiinflammatory effects⁵⁸ while a direct antiviral effect of statin is not completely out of the realm of possibility. Meanwhile, the potential anticancer effects⁵⁹ of statins and the statin reduced^{60, 61} cancer-related mortality attracted increasing attention of scholars. Simvastatin demonstrated more benefits for lung cancer patients than pravastatin.^{62, 63} Even Atorvastatin had potential anticancer effects.^{64, 65} However, inconsistent results on these relationship have been reported too. Atorvastatin^{66, 67} (AVT), is able to suppress⁶⁸ tumour^{69, 70} cell growth too and is potentially protective⁷¹ against the development of lung⁷² cancer.

Vikas Khurana et al.⁷³ investigated in a retrospective case-control study (N = 483,733 patients) whether the use of statins prior to the diagnosis of lung cancer has any protective effect against the development of lung cancer. The accuracy of the intake of the medication was not guaranteed.

⁵⁸Horne BD, Muhlestein JB, Carlquist JF, Bair TL, Madsen TE, Hart NI, Anderson JL; Intermountain Heart Collaborative (IHC) Study Group. Statin therapy interacts with cytomegalovirus seropositivity and high C-reactive protein in reducing mortality among patients with angiographically significant coronary disease. *Circulation*. 2003 Jan 21;107(2):258-63. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.0000045668.71683.92. PMID: 12538425.

⁵⁹Xia DK, Hu ZG, Tian YF, Zeng FJ. Statin use and prognosis of lung cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies and randomized controlled trials. *Drug Des Devel Ther*. 2019 Jan 23;13:405-422. doi: 10.2147/DDDT.S187690. PMID: 30774306; PMCID: PMC6350654.

⁶⁰Nielsen SF, Nordestgaard BG, Bojesen SE. Statin use and reduced cancer-related mortality. *N Engl J Med*. 2012 Nov 8;367(19):1792-802. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1201735. PMID: 23134381.

⁶¹Li X, Wu XB, Chen Q. Statin use is not associated with reduced risk of skin cancer: a meta-analysis. *Br J Cancer*. 2014 Feb 4;110(3):802-7. doi: 10.1038/bjc.2013.762. Epub 2013 Dec 24. PMID: 24366301; PMCID: PMC3915126.

⁶²Cardwell CR, Mc Menamin Ú, Hughes CM, Murray LJ. Statin use and survival from lung cancer: a population-based cohort study. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev*. 2015 May;24(5):833-41. doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-15-0052. PMID: 25934831.

⁶³Hwang KE, Kwon SJ, Kim YS, Park DS, Kim BR, Yoon KH, Jeong ET, Kim HR. Effect of simvastatin on the resistance to EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors in a non-small cell lung cancer with the T790M mutation of EGFR. *Exp Cell Res*. 2014 May 1;323(2):288-96. doi: 10.1016/j.yexcr.2014.02.026. Epub 2014 Mar 12. PMID: 24631288.

⁶⁴Chen J, Liu B, Yuan J, Yang J, Zhang J, An Y, Tie L, Pan Y, Li X. Atorvastatin reduces vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) expression in human non-small cell lung carcinomas (NSCLCs) via inhibition of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production. *Mol Oncol*. 2012 Feb;6(1):62-72. doi: 10.1016/j.molonc.2011.11.003. Epub 2011 Nov 22. PMID: 22153388; PMCID: PMC5528383.

⁶⁵Chen J, Lan T, Hou J, Zhang J, An Y, Tie L, Pan Y, Liu J, Li X. Atorvastatin sensitizes human non-small cell lung carcinomas to carboplatin via suppression of AKT activation and upregulation of TIMP-1. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol*. 2012 May;44(5):759-69. doi: 10.1016/j.biocel.2012.01.015. Epub 2012 Jan 25. PMID: 22305890.

⁶⁶Lin JJ, Ezer N, Sigel K, Mhango G, Wisnivesky JP. The effect of statins on survival in patients with stage IV lung cancer. *Lung Cancer*. 2016 Sep;99:137-42. doi: 10.1016/j.lungcan.2016.07.006. Epub 2016 Jul 6. PMID: 27565929; PMCID: PMC5003323.

⁶⁷Xia DK, Hu ZG, Tian YF, Zeng FJ. Statin use and prognosis of lung cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies and randomized controlled trials. *Drug Des Devel Ther*. 2019 Jan 23;13:405-422. doi: 10.2147/DDDT.S187690. PMID: 30774306; PMCID: PMC6350654.

⁶⁸Vallianou NG, Kostantinou A, Kougias M, Kazazis C. Statins and cancer. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem*. 2014 Jun;14(5):706-12. doi: 10.2174/1871520613666131129105035. PMID: 24295174.

⁶⁹Cafforio P, Dammacco F, Gernone A, Silvestris F. Statins activate the mitochondrial pathway of apoptosis in human lymphoblasts and myeloma cells. *Carcinogenesis*. 2005 May;26(5):883-91. doi: 10.1093/carcin/bgi036. Epub 2005 Feb 10. PMID: 15705602.

⁷⁰Kaushal V, Kohli M, Mehta P, Mehta JL. Potential anticancer effects of statins: fact or fiction? *Endothelium*. 2003;10(1):49-58. doi: 10.1080/106233203033358. PMID: 12699077.

⁷¹Gray J, Alberts WM, Bepler G. Statins and lung cancer risk. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1274-5. doi: 10.1378/chest.07-0308. PMID: 17494775.

⁷²<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8720807/>

⁷³Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

Still, Vikas Khurana et al. found that the protective effect of statin therapy against lung cancer increased with the duration of statin therapy. Among those who used statin for 4 years and more there was a 77% reduction for lung cancer.

Table 9. Statin therapy (> 4 year) and lung cancer (Study of Khurana et al., 2007).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 4 year	YES	269	49739	50008
	NO	7011	426714	433725
		7280	476453	483733

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship k = -0,02697061
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99944391
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99462086
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,96304945

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 1,44698848
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 9,93969780
P Value (EXCL) = 0,00055594

PROPORTIONS.
(a/A) × 100 = (269 / 50008) × 100 = 0,54 %
(b/A) × 100 = (49739 / 50008) × 100 = 99,46 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (7011 / 433725) × 100 = 1,62 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (426714 / 433725) × 100 = 98,38 %
(a/B) × 100 = (269 / 7280) × 100 = 3,70 %
(c/B) × 100 = (7011 / 7280) × 100 = 96,30 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (49739 / 476453) × 100 = 10,44 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (426714 / 476453) × 100 = 89,56 %
(A/N) × 100 = (50008 / 483733) × 100 = 10,34 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (433725 / 483733) × 100 = 89,66 %
(B/N) × 100 = (7280 / 483733) × 100 = 1,50 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (476453 / 483733) × 100 = 98,50 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,33277239
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,35395163
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 66,72 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,32916387
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,64257319

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU) = 0,88157103
p(IOI) = 0,08832972

The study design (p(IOI) = 0,08832972) of the study of Khurana et al. was suitable enough, but not optimal. In the optimal case, the placebo group should have been enlarged up to 7 times more to a sample size of 3.000.000 million subjects. In other words, the exclusion relationship between statin therapy > 4 years and lung cancer will be much stronger than suggested by the data of the study of Khurana et al. It should be noted, however, that a long-term therapy with statins is almost as effective against lung cancer (p(EXCL)= 0,99944391; P Value = 0,00055594) as a vaccination with Pfizer/Biontech's mRNA vaccine against Covid 19 (p(EXCL)= 1-(8/43448) = 0,999815872; P Value =

0,000184128).⁷⁴,⁷⁵ This is quite a surprising result, and we understandably ask ourselves how this can be? Does the data of Khurana et al. represent objective reality very accurately? More or less, it seems to be that statins have anti-inflammatory properties. Kang et al.⁷⁶ (Division of Pulmonology, Department of Internal Medicine, Severance Hospital, Yonsei University College of Medicine, Seoul, Republic of Korea) conducted a retrospective cohort study based on the South Korean nationwide claims database to evaluate whether statin use affects the development⁷⁷ of tuberculosis (TB). The data published by Kang et al. (see table 10) support even the claim that statins are protecting against the development of tuberculosis with a probability of $p(\text{EXCL}) = (1 - (504 / (840899))) = 0.99940064$ (P Value = 0.00059918).

Table 10. Statin therapy and Tuberculosis (Study of Kang et al., 2014).

		Tuberculosis		
		YES	NO	
Statins	YES	504	158694	159198
	NO	3571	678130	681701
		4075	836824	840899
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.				
		Causal relationship k =	-0,01169174	
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) =			0,00000000	
		p (EXCL) =	0,99940064	
P Value (EXCL) =			0,00059918	
		p(IOI)=	0,18447281	

Therefore, statins are potentially effective against *Mycobacterium avium* subspecies paratuberculosis (MAP) and of use for Morbus Crohn too. Incredibly amazing, several publications support our belief that statins have beneficial anti-inflammatory properties, especially against CMV⁷⁸, including the the study of Benjamin D Horne et al.⁷⁹ Under the justified assumption that this more than just theoretically possible relationship can be confirmed by other study groups too, another question is straightforward and mandatory. Is there any causal influence of CMV on lung cancer?⁸⁰

⁷⁴Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

⁷⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2021). COVID-19 vaccines - a great leap forward?. *Causation*, 6(12), 5–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779506>, p. 42.

⁷⁶Kang YA, Choi NK, Seong JM, Heo EY, Koo BK, Hwang SS, Park BJ, Yim JJ, Lee CH. The effects of statin use on the development of tuberculosis among patients with diabetes mellitus. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2014 Jun;18(6):717-24. doi: 10.5588/ijtld.13.0854. Erratum in: *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2015 May;19(5):622. PMID: 24903944.

⁷⁷Guerra-De-Blas PDC, Torres-González P, Bobadilla-Del-Valle M, Sada-Ovalle I, Ponce-De-León-Garduño A, Sifuentes-Osorio J. Potential Effect of Statins on *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Infection. *J Immunol Res.* 2018 Nov 15;2018:7617023. doi: 10.1155/2018/7617023. PMID: 30581876; PMCID: PMC6276473.

⁷⁸Ponroy N, Taveira A, Mueller NJ, Millard AL. Statins demonstrate a broad anti-cytomegalovirus activity in vitro in ganciclovir-susceptible and resistant strains. *J Med Virol.* 2015 Jan;87(1):141-53. doi:10.1002/jmv.23998. Epub 2014 Jun 27. See: PMID: 24976258.

⁷⁹Horne BD, Muhlestein JB, Carlquist JF, Bair TL, Madsen TE, Hart NI, Anderson JL; Intermountain Heart Collaborative (IHC) Study Group. Statin therapy interacts with cytomegalovirus seropositivity and high C-reactive protein in reducing mortality among patients with angiographically significant coronary disease. *Circulation.* 2003 Jan 21;107(2):258-63. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.0000045668.71683.92. PMID: 12538425.

⁸⁰Du X, Li D, Wang G, Fan Y, Li N, Chai L, Li G, Li J. Chemoprotective effect of atorvastatin against benzo(a)pyrene-induced lung cancer via the inhibition of oxidative stress and inflammatory parameters. *Ann Transl Med.* 2021 Feb;9(4):355. doi: 10.21037/atm-20-7770. PMCID: PMC7944302 PMID: 33708982. Erratum in: *Ann Transl Med.* 2021 Jul;9(14):1214. PMID: 33708982; PMCID:

4. Discussion

As was to be expected, the data of the studies presented are very contradictory. But despite all the ups and downs, there is one trend that cannot be overlooked. More or less, the studies quite clearly support the necessary condition relationship. In other words, without a CMV infection, no BD (see table 2 and table 3). The study by Sun et al. was able to provide evidence that CMV is a sufficient condition of BD (see table 1). The formal prerequisites for considering the possibility of a causal relationship between CMV and BD would thus be given. The PCR-based study by Sun et al. actually provided evidence that CMV is the cause of BD (see table 1). Of course, other questions arise in this context. Was the diagnosis of BD made correctly and according to the same criteria by all study groups and so on? However, despite all the difficulties, the evidence presented in this publication is quite clear.

5. Conclusion

We have a slight degree of evidence to draw the following conclusion.

‘Cytomegalovirus is the cause of Adamantiades-Behçet’s disease.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications

[PMC7944302.](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PMC7944302/)

does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^e<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^f<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^g<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

ⁱ<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^jhttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^khttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>